

Studies on Stability and Electrokinetic Potential of Barium Sulphate Sol

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A highly purified barium sulphate sol has been prepared by Kato's method followed by dialysis for one week. The true electrokinetic potential of this sol for a given slow rate of coagulation has been determined by electro-osmotic as well as by electrophoretic methods using the Smoluchowski equation with correction for surface conductance. The true zeta-potential for rapid coagulation obtained from electro-osmotic data has been found to be slightly less than that for the slow one.

Attempts have been made by many authors to correlate the stability of a colloid with its electrical charge. Previous experimental results of Powis¹, Mukherjee *et al.*², Kruyt *et al.*³ and Ghosh⁴ on As_2S_3 sol and of Kruyt *et al.*⁵ and Weiser *et al.*⁶ on AgI sol do not lend support to either Hardy's theory⁷ of coagulation at the isoelectric point or Powis's theory⁸ of coagulation at a critical potential. According to Hermans⁹, Verwey and Overbeek¹⁰, Rutgers¹¹, and Bikerman¹², use of the Smoluchowski equation¹³ in calculating zeta-potential may lead to considerable error.

Applying surface conductivity correction, Rutgers¹¹ has shown that true zeta-potential (ζ) can be evaluated by using the equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta SE_1}{DP} \left(1 + \frac{2\chi}{rS}\right) = \zeta_1 \left(1 + \frac{2\chi}{rS}\right)$$

where E_1 = streaming potential, P = pressure used for forcing the liquid through a uniform capillary tube of radius ' r ' in contact with water or dilute electrolyte, S , = specific conductance of the liquid in bulk, χ = specific surface conductance, η is the coefficient of viscosity, and D , the dielectric constant, ζ_1 , being the apparent zeta-potential. It has been shown by Overbeek and Wijga¹⁴ that for a porous diaphragm made of powdered glass,

1. Powis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734.
2. Mukherjee *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1928, 5, 735.
3. Kruyt *et al.*, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 170.
4. Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2693.
5. Kruyt *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 78, 32.
6. Weiser *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 179.
7. Hardy, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900, A66, 110.
8. Powis, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 186.
9. Hermans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 133.
10. Verwey and Overbeek, "Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", 1948.
11. Rutgers, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 69.
12. Bikerman, *ibid.*, 1940, 36, 154.
13. Smoluchowski, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, 93, 129.
14. Overbeek and Wijga, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1946, 65, 656.

the above equation fails. Ghosh¹⁵ has shown from Wijga's data that the true zeta-potential of pyrex glass can be evaluated with the help of the equation,

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{2\alpha x}{rS} \right)$$

where α is a correction factor for the diaphragm. Recently Ghosh¹⁶ has deduced the equation:

$$\frac{\zeta}{\zeta_a} = 1 + \frac{3x}{aR} \cdot \frac{1}{S}$$

(where R = radius of particles forming the diaphragm; a = ratio of volume of liquid to the volume of solid in the diaphragm), for the evaluation of true zeta-potential (ζ) of fine particles forming a diaphragm. It has been verified by Ghosh *et al.*¹⁷ and others on a number of colloids. The above equation can also be written as

$$\frac{\zeta}{\zeta_a} = 1 + \frac{3r}{2aR} \left(\frac{2x}{rS} \right) = 1 + \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{V_1}{V_2} \cdot \frac{r}{R} \left(\frac{2x}{rS} \right) = 1 + \alpha \cdot \frac{2x}{rS}$$

or $\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{2\alpha x}{r\zeta S} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{S}$ (i)

where r = average radius of a typical pore in the diaphragm.

It has also been shown by Ghosh *et al.*¹⁸ that a similar expression

$$1/\zeta_a = 1/\zeta + m'/S \quad (\text{ii})$$

for electrophoresis can be found from the equation of Booth¹⁹ and Henry²⁰ for large values of (ka) and for non-conducting particles where a is the radius of the particle and k the reciprocal of the thickness of the electrical double layer.

In the present paper we shall record the results of our experiments on barium sulphate sol.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Preparation of the Sol by Kato's Method*²¹.—A molar solution of sulphuric acid diluted with twice its volume of alcohol was poured in a thin stream into a molar solution of barium acetate, diluted with five times its volume of ethanol. The bluish sol thus obtained was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure below 40° when a translucent mass was left as residue. This was then dispersed in water giving a fluorescent sol which was dialys-

15. Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 274, 393.
16. Ghosh, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 1977.
17. Ghosh *et al.*, *Science & Culture* 1953, **18**, 498.
18. Ghosh *et al.*, *Nature*, 1955, **176**, 1081.
19. Booth, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 955.
20. Henry, *ibid.*, 1948, **44**, 1021.
21. Kato, *Mem. Coll. Sci. Kyoto Imp. Univ.*, 1909, **2**, 187.

ed against distilled water for 7 days and stored in a Jena flask for 15 days. The positively charged sol is milky white. Its $pH=7.2$, specific conductance at $25^{\circ}=5.65 \times 10^{-3}$ mhos and barium sulphate content= 4.15 g/100ml.

Determination of the Equicoagulating Concentration of Electrolytes

(a) *Rapid Rate of Coagulation.*—A definite volume of the sol (5ml) was mixed with the same volume of an electrolyte solution of the desired concentration and the mixture was left to itself for 15 minutes. When coagulation was complete, a sharp boundary was formed between the coagula and the intermicellary fluid. The exact concentrations of different electrolytes, which coagulate the sol in a given time, was determined by trial.

(b) *Slow Rate of Coagulation.*—In this case, the colloid mixed with an equal volume of electrolyte solution was left to itself for 18 hours and was then centrifuged for exactly 2 minutes with a definite speed. The minimum concentration of the electrolyte, which just produced a transparent supernatant solution after centrifuging, was taken to be the equicoagulation value.

Electro-osmotic Experiments at 25°

A given volume (50 ml) of the sol was mixed with an equal volume of electrolyte of equicoagulating concentration and the mixture was allowed to stand for 18 hours for slow and 15 minutes for rapid rates of coagulation. The coagula, separated from the supernatant liquid by centrifuging, were then transferred to a U-shaped tube. To obtain a compact diaphragm, the U-tube was centrifuged at a given speed. The volume of the diaphragm in each experiment was made the same as far as possible by regulating the time of centrifuging. This ensured constancy in the value of ' m ' in equation (i) provided χ remains constant at the equicoagulating point. The U-tube containing the diaphragm was filled with supernatant liquid. The electroendosmotic velocity was then measured by Mukherjee's²² method.

Electrophoretic Experiments at 25°

A modified form of Burton's U-tube apparatus²³ was used for the purpose. The sol (20 ml) was mixed with the electrolyte of equicoagulating concentration. The mixture was allowed to stand for half an hour after which it was centrifuged for 2 minutes to allow the bigger particles to settle. The supernatant mixture was then used for filling the lower part of the U-tube. The solution filling the upper part of the U-tube was prepared previously by mixing 100 ml of sol with 100 ml of electrolyte of proper concentration and removing the colloidal particles by centrifuging after 24 hours. Ag/AgCl electrodes were used and the coagulant selected was either chloride alone or mixtures of chloride with other negatively charged ions.

The movement of the colloid-liquid boundary was noted under a given current and the mean value of the upward and downward motion in a given time was recorded.

22. Mukherjee, *this Journal*, 1927, 4, 493.

23. Ghosh *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, 158, 45.

Specific conductance and *pH* of the supernatant solution were also measured. The *pH* values of the different supernatant solutions were found to be practically the same^{7,15}

DISCUSSION

In the zone of rapid coagulation, the values of apparent electrokinetic potential ζ_a calculated with the help of Smoluchowski equation vary from 6.3 mv to 20.5 mv, the surface conductance effect being very marked. It may be noticed from Fig. 1, that a linear relationship exists between $1/\zeta_a$ and $1/S$, where *S* is the specific conductance of the supernatant solution. Corresponding to two sets of electrolytes two straight lines I and II are obtained with different slopes (viz. 5.225×10^{-6} and 5.0×10^{-6} respectively) meeting the $1/\zeta_a$ axis at the same point. The reciprocal of the intercept on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis gives the true zeta potential to be 25 mv. The two straight lines having different values of *m* may be attributed to different values of τ or to different values of χ both of which are included in *m*.

FIG. 1

From Figs. 2 and 3, it may be noticed that the linear relationship also holds for electro-osmosis as well as electrophoresis in the zone of slow coagulation. The surface conductance correction, however, is less marked in the electrophoretic method than in the electro-osmotic one, as can be noticed from the values of *m*. Consequently the values of ζ_a found from electrophoresis are somewhat higher than the corresponding values found from electro-osmosis. In the zone of slow coagulation, also, both in electro-osmosis and electrophoresis, two straight lines (I) and (II) are obtained with different slopes, corresponding to two sets of electrolytes used (vide Figs. 2 and 3).

The extrapolated values of true zeta-potential are found to be 28.6 mv and 30.7 mv in electro-osmosis and electrophoresis respectively. These values lie within the limits of experimental error and their average 29.6 mv may be taken to represent the true ζ for the region of slow coagulation.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The results thus lead to the conclusion that a given rate of coagulation is characterised by a definite value of true zeta-potential. Again it may be noticed from the Figs. 1-3, that for a change in the time of coagulation from 15 mins. to 18 hrs., the corresponding change in the values of true zeta-potential is relatively small (25 mv to 29.6 mv). We may therefore conclude that a critical zone of zeta-potential exists for the coagulation of barium sulphate sol by different electrolytes.

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